

The Virtuoso Composer and the Formidable Machine: A Path to Preserving Human Compositional Expression

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ABSTRACT

Many contemporary computer music systems can emulate aspects of composers' behaviour, creating and arranging structural elements traditionally manipulated by composers. This raises the question as to how new computer music systems can act as effective tools that enable composers to express their personal musical vision—if a computer is acting as a composer's tool, but is working directly with score structure, how can it preserve the composer's artistic voice? David Wessel and Matthew Wright have argued that, in the case of musical instrument interfaces, a balance should be struck between ease of use and the potential for developing expressivity through virtuosity. In this paper, we adapt these views to the design of compositional interfaces. We introduce the idea of the virtuoso composer, and propose an understanding of computer music systems that may enhance the relationship between composers and their computer software tools, particularly with regard to the composition of tonal music and related traditional forms. We conclude by arguing for a conceptualization of the composer/computer relationship that supports the continued development of human expression and creativity in compositional activities.

1. INTRODUCTION

In this article we introduce the idea of the virtuoso composer. We advocate for a perspective on (composition-oriented) computer music system design that allows composers to express their musical vision effectively and transparently. We suggest that, like a virtuosic instrumentalist, the virtuoso composer works with an instrument upon which they can achieve mastery, *i.e.* a computer software system that may extend his or her compositional capabilities and support the expression of original, personal compositional ideas.

We choose to describe the composer who excels at the use of a computer music environment as a virtuoso because, like a virtuoso instrumentalist, the expression of their ideas can depend on the skill with which they can use their expressive tool, in this case a computer music system. The act of composition, of creating music through interaction

with software system, does not necessarily occur in real time (as in the case of a performer playing on, for example, a violin). Nevertheless, like a violinist, a composer who writes music with the aid of a computer-based tool may benefit from experience with that software system, learning to exploit its inherent capabilities and work around its limitations through practice and study. The result is that, like a musical instrument, a system designed to enable a composer to create new musical compositions can result in more individual music (as measured, for example, by its success in projecting the expressive or intellectual aims of the composer) once the composer has achieved mastery with that system. The design of such a system may become an important factor governing that composer's workflow. This is similar to the manner in which a musician who plays the violin may find that they can achieve maximum expression only through use of that instrument; a trumpet, or even a cello, may not yield a similar degree of musical expressivity to the virtuoso violinist, despite the advanced state of his or her musical knowledge and accomplishment.

The question may be asked: how can this conception of the composer and his or her computer tools influence how a developer designs and implements a computer-based composition environment? Furthermore, does the computer, by actively taking over aspects of compositional processes traditionally in the domain of the composer, reduce or magnify the transmission of the composer's ideas? Please note that while we understand the diversity of compositional structures available to the modern composer, this paper deals primarily with tonal and traditional musical forms, an area of composition which we feel is still relevant due to its popularity and its prevalence in interactive media scores.

2. COMPUTERS AS CREATIVE TOOLS

As computers become adept at manipulating elements of score structure traditionally defined by the human composer, these composers may begin to face an existential crisis. There are ample examples of computer systems that surpass human capability: in head-to-head matches IBM's *Deep Blue* defeated the ranking chess grandmaster of its time [1], a system called *Watson* beat two *Jeopardy* champions in a trivia contest [2] and David Cope's *Experiments in Musical Intelligence* software has famously fooled a musically educated audience into believing that its own generated output was actually composed by J. S. Bach [3]. If a computer can successfully emulate aspects of composers'

activities, how can a composer working with such a system take ownership of the music produced with it? Will the human composer even be necessary or desirable, when such systems reach sufficiently advanced states of development?

2.1 What the Composer Brings to Music

The above questions may lead us to ask what a human composer brings to music. One possible answer, founded on comparisons between music produced with samples versus “authentic” instrumental performance, might relate to the idea of “expression”. With regard to music composed with the aid of computer music systems, the composer is arguably best served when something of significance expressed by that composer can be identified within the musical output of the overall system. The degree to which they are served is a reflection of the degree to which their expressive choices, as evidence of their artistic voice, are preserved in the system’s musical output. Under this definition, the most transparently expressive compositional technology might be the pencil, for it arguably adds nothing of substance to the composer’s creation, serving totally as an extension of the composer’s own creative processes.

However, composing with a pencil is extremely challenging, making significant demands upon a composer’s memory, sight-reading skill, and ability to sustain musical imagery. The simple pencil is thus an extraordinarily demanding compositional tool. Alternatively, the use of a computer as a compositional aid can alleviate some of these issues. For example, a computer can act as an externalized memory, since it can play back a score, providing a aural representation of a musical work at any point in a composition, diminishing the composer’s need to memorize the position and role of each written note. A simple pencil cannot do this.

A computer is often viewed as a source of human empowerment. Early in the development of computers, the devices were seen as a means to improve life and extend human ability, such as Vannevar Bush’s theoretical *Memex*, an information-storage device which would, had it been achievable at the time, have aided in the preservation and dissemination of knowledge [4]. Other advancements such as Engelbart’s computer-centric innovations (such as the mouse, window and word processor) were designed to help humanity deal with increasingly complex problems by “augmenting human intellect” [5]. This view of technology as enriching human experience seems to continue to resonate today as consumers pursue new technologies (*e.g.* tablet computers, smartwatches and social media) and improvements in existing technologies (such as video game consoles with faster processors and more storage space). It can be difficult to see why traditional technology like a pencil could be at all superior to a specially-designed computer program that allows a composer to write more rapidly, and with subjectively more impressive results, than that composer would have achieved had they been forced to wield a more humble tool. Does the incorporation of computer technology and agency into human musical activities have any potentially negative impacts upon creativity?

2.2 What the Computer can Take from the Composer

One line of enquiry relevant to this question involves an examination of how compositional skill may be replaced by computer technology. Evidence for the possibility of a computer-based compositional system to supplant compositional skill may be found in the case of Rachael Y., a composer with an acquired brain injury that caused an amusia (specifically a loss of the ability to sustain musical imagery) [6]. Prior to her accident Rachael had composed in her head, working out score structures in her imagination before committing them to paper. After her accident, she could no longer sustain the memory of her musical ideas, and composing using internal musical imagery became impossible for her. Yet she was able to return to composing despite lacking the ability to sustain the memory of her music: on the advice of a collaborator, she learned to use a computer to record and play back her musical ideas, reducing the load on her own memory. Thus, by adopting a computer system as a substitute for her own damaged cognitive systems (and with the aid of her collaborator), she once again became an active composer. In one post-accident instance, she created a partially autobiographic musical work that reflected her “rediscovery of identity” [6]. The work is deeply personal, but it must be acknowledged that the composition could only exist because of the aid of the composition software she used.

By extension, those composers who take advantage of a computer-based composition environment by using it as an external aid to memory (even if just to review the final mix of a composition to check for pitch errors) may be said to be benefitting from an externalized substitute for processes that composers who lack such technology would normally have to undertake themselves. And if such computer-using composers are unable or unwilling to learn how to enact these creative processes themselves, they risk becoming dependent on their computer-based tool, in a way that they could not were they only using a simple pencil. While pencil-based composers are comparatively limited in the sense that they lack a tool that allows them to listen to their scores before handing them to any musicians, they are also enhanced by the experience of learning to use the pencil: they develop a facility with their memory and mental imagery that may exceed those they would have possessed had they began their compositional development with the reliance on software systems that obviated the need for such extremely developed mental abilities.

3. THE VIRTUOSO INSTRUMENTALIST

Virtuosos may be described as “human beings that excel in their practice to the point of exhibiting exceptional performance.” [7] It is common to apply this label to instrumentalists who excel in performance upon an instrument, and history makes mention of many virtuoso musicians from Paganini to Hendrix. Yet historically, the virtuoso does not merely perform with facility; he or she must, through performance, *express* his or her own interpretation of the musical work being performed. The success of that interpretation can be a criterion for the judgement of the virtuosity

of their performance [8].

Another significant aspect of instrumental virtuosity is that it represents action at “the limit of human capacities” [7]. Virtuosity is no commonplace human attribute; it is a manifestation of rare skill or talent, and is not immediately available to the typical performer. Nevertheless, attempts to model musical virtuosity in automated improvising systems, such as Pachet’s bebop phrase generator [7], have demonstrated that it is possible to understand or codify some of the processes that go into a virtuosic performance. Such an understanding is exhibited by some virtuoso musicians themselves—for example Mark Levine, an accomplished jazz pianist, has said that most of what goes into the production of a great jazz solo is both explainable and teachable [9]. Yet Levine also asserts that a great deal of thought and practise will still be required of prospective jazz virtuosos, in the same way that Pachet’s bebop phrase generator required thorough analysis of the structure of existing jazz improvisations.

In terms of designing computer-based musical instruments that may support virtuosic performance, David Wessel and Matthew Wright present a perspective that proves helpful. They first argue [10] that a properly-programmed computer and interface may constitute a musical instrument. Performing music on a computer through use of a gestural interface is akin to performing on a traditional instrument such as a violin or piano. With traditional instruments, the musician is in direct control of the means of sound production. In the case of a computer system, the user controls the event-level progression of musical ideas, which Wessel and Wright argue may be most effective under a “one-gesture-to-one-acoustic-event” paradigm.

Wessel and Wright go on to examine the distinctions between instrument forms. One of the more effective ways to compare different musical instruments is based on ease-of-use. Wessel and Wright suggest that not all instruments are equally easy to perform upon, and they introduce two related factors: the ease with which an instrument can be used by an individual unfamiliar with it, and the degree to which continued practice upon the instrument promotes the development of an expressive virtuosity. In designing a musical instrument, whether computer-based or not, one is creating a system which will challenge its performer to some degree, and yield an output of particular expressive qualities. These two properties can be related, in that more difficult musical instruments often require more subtle or precise control from their performers, and that this control complexity can be associated with a greater number of dimensions of modulation. For example, the violin, often considered an extremely challenging instrument, has many control dimensions (including bow pressure and speed, rate of vibrato and fingering position), each of which can contribute to expressive variation in the violinist’s performance. The instrument rewards those who commit the (often considerable) time needed to achieve mastery with the ability to use the instrument with greater expressive freedom.

4. THE VIRTUOSO COMPOSER

In traditional Western tonal music the composer works in the domain of the structural elements that are found in a musical score: pitch, timing, dynamics and timbral choices that, customarily, are not to be altered significantly by a performer. Expressive choices are available to the performer, but they should always be consistent with the musical structure represented in the score. Each note in a score is part of a statement of the composer’s creative imagination.

Yet computer software systems are increasingly used by composers as tools to realize their compositions. Furthermore, computer systems themselves can take autonomous roles in the composition process, manipulating music structure independently of the composer. Some well-known systems allow for minimal expressive interaction, such as David Cope’s *Experiments in Musical Intelligence*. [11] Others are built around the idea of promoting interaction, such as David Rokeby’s *Very Nervous System* [12]. An illustrative example of a system that combines expression with compositional elements may be found in *Bloom*, a popular iOS app by Brian Eno and Peter Chilvers [13].

4.1 Creativity and *Bloom*

Bloom is a generative music system that functions in a semi-autonomous manner [14]. It blurs the line between composition and performance, but we would argue that it can be considered a composing tool since it allows users access to musical score structures (*e.g.* pitch and timing) normally manipulated by composers. The generated musical environment consists of two layers. One is a background “pad” sound defining a tonal centre and overall mood. The user of *Bloom* can add another layer to this musical backdrop by tapping on the screen. For each tap, the app responds by playing a note that conforms to the overall tonal nature of the music at that moment in time, and the pitch and rhythmic placement of the note is partly governed by where and when the user taps.

It may be impossible for any user, even a musically-untrained one, to play an “incorrect”-sounding note when using *Bloom*, due to the manner in which it translates user taps into musical notes. The user’s performance always results in notes that enhance the calming mood of the underlying pad. Yet the subjective experience of the user is that they are in control of the music, since their taps seem to map directly to the timing and pitch of the generated notes.

Does *Bloom* make any user into an instant composer? Certainly *Bloom* does allow the user access to musical score structure, which is within the domain of the composer. However, using the app does not grant much expressive freedom—the result is always going to be similar, regardless of who is performing, because the app takes over many of the creative decisions that are normally afforded to the composer (*e.g.* the precise definition of note pitches, the exact timing of musical notes, the key of the piece, and so forth).

We have argued that expressivity is necessary for virtuosity, and *Bloom* does not grant this aspect of control to

any great extent. Under Wessel and Wright's view, *Bloom* may be the compositional equivalent to a kazoo, with an easy entry fee for a would-be composer, but a lack of the expressive performance capabilities necessary to promote virtuosity with the app. *Bloom* may allow its users access to some basic choices that composers make, but as a creative composing tool, it is fairly limited. The other aspect of virtuosity we describe, its tendency to require sustained effort to achieve, is also not in evidence in the use of *Bloom*: if all compositions made using the app are similar in structure or form, how can a user strive to achieve a transcendent level of expressivity with the software? If the practised user cannot exceed the effect of a novice, then virtuosity is impossible.

4.2 Computer Music Composition Systems As Virtuosoic Tools

A computer-based composition environment that supports the development of virtuosity must do what *Bloom* cannot: offer its users the ability to express their individual ideas, and reward them with heightened expressive power through engaging with the system. What properties would such a system, if successfully implemented, possess?

If an ultimate tool enabling virtuosoic self-expression for composers is the pencil, that may serve as an initial model. There are already numerous composing environments available to composers to record their ideas (e.g. notation software such as *Sibelius* and *Finale*, the sequencers *Cubase* and *Logic*), but computers can act as more than mere recording devices. A defining component of computers is their processor, which enables independent manipulation of musical structure. The computer processor is the computer music system's key advantage over a pencil, in part because it allows the computer to perform a work differently each time it is initiated.

In his influential essay "What a Musical Work is", Jerrold Levinson argues that "a musical work must be capable of being created, must be individuated by context of composition, and must be inclusive of means of performance" [15]. A typical musical work of the Western tonal idiom (which was the domain of Levinson's argument) has a specific composer who wrote it at a specific time and has defined its instrumentation. A computer music artwork need not conform to this definition, since the computer can act as an agent that modifies musical structure in response to its listeners, the ambient environment, and the will of its composer (whether or not the composer is actually present at the time and engaged with the performance). This is arguably the greatest contribution of computers to music composition: a musical work is no longer a single score structure composed by an individual, but rather a super-set from which many musical structures may be derived. Each performance of *Bloom* generates a specific musical score, but *Bloom* itself is much more than a score, as it comprises all possible score structures that may be derived from it through interaction. The computer's agency elevates the computer music work above a mere score, adding a dimension to the archetypal musical work that was impossible before computer processing of musical scores was

developed.

As van Geelen argues, while "interactive audio has its roots in linear audio," it need not be confined to the form [16]. Computational agency, when incorporated into a composer's workflow, adds a dimension to a musical work that has yet to be fully explored or understood by contemporary artist/composers. Computer music systems that enable non-linear music represent an immense artistic opportunity, a new frontier for creativity. Yet some systems, such as *Bloom* or David Cope's *Experiments in Musical Intelligence*, assume so much responsibility for defining the event-to-event structure of their musical output that they deny the composer the freedom to explore the creative possibilities of this new artistic frontier. In other words, they do not allow composers to achieve virtuosity with their systems, robbing them of the opportunity to skillfully express their individual musical ideas. It would be tragic if the creative opportunities afforded by integrating computational agency into the creation of dynamic music were to be negated by system designers who fail to give the composer a chance to engage in personal self-expression.

We thus encounter a conundrum. In order to progress into an era of interactive music, composers will need access to computer systems that can transform musical ideas during a performance (and without the real-time intervention of the composer) in response to their environment. Yet to transfer the power to restructure musical ideas to computer software negates some of the expressive contributions of the composer. How can a computer scientist design a computer-based system for composers that allows them creative and expressive freedom, while still maintaining the ability to produce music that adapts to its ambient environment?

Currently we can provide no definitive answer to this question; however, we can provide a perspective that may support the eventual realization of such a system: when designing computer music systems to support *human* compositional creativity, begin with an understanding of the pencil. By requiring more of its user than he or she is initially comfortable with, by subjecting him or her to a period of rigorous study and sometimes uncomfortable struggle, the pencil enforces an elevation of skill and mental faculties even as it transmits an individual's creative expression in unaltered form. While computers have provided humanity with quick solutions to difficult problems, the designers of new systems for creating music should remember that they are involved in processes relating to the creation of musical art, and that art has been a deeply human expression. Such researchers are actually building upon centuries of musical development through which great composers have provided moments of transcendent emotional experience. If their system designs are to tap into this rich vein of creative activity, they must not push aside the composer's intentions by replacing them with a powerful but self-contained computational agency. Truly dynamic music that responds in real time to its listeners and may ultimately possess an awareness of its environment is becoming a reality, an opportunity for composers to redefine and reinvigorate the musical arts (which, it must be said, have

in recent times been accused of failing to find a balance between innovation and popular appeal [17].) To lose this opportunity because the tools necessary to engage directly and meaningfully with it were never developed would diminish music and reveal a particular lack of foresight on the part of computer music system designers.

4.3 A Way Forward

The composer who excels in expressing their original ideas through a computer music system can be as much a virtuoso as a great violinist. The fact that their score is not output in real time does not diminish the value of the composer's struggles with their instrument, learning to exploit its limitations, and ultimately becoming skilled enough to draw from it music that expresses profound emotion in an innovative manner. When these ideas can be expressed dynamically, with the computer responding to the performance environment while still transmitting the inspirations of the composer, a new musical art form may evolve.

Yet without the tools to realize this revolutionary new musical development, the future for music may be bleaker, with the computer becoming the source of musical invention and the human musical spirit weakening.

There is a movement gaining strength today known as "Ubiquitous Music" or UbiMus, which in part seeks to increase the accessibility and spread of creative and artistic tools, including outside of traditional studio settings [18]. Proponents of the movement have argued that "all humans are creative" and as a result will benefit from opportunities to engage in self-expression [19]. We agree that this perspective is valid and that to support the design of creative tools for all people (whether or not they have training in an art form) is one of the most exciting opportunities afforded by ubiquitous computer technology today. Yet there may be a temptation to make the "entry fee" for using a new technology lower, to make it accessible to more people. We would suggest that doing so may lead to systems that fail to support compositional virtuosity, in turn diminishing their creative and expressive potential.

5. CONCLUSION

We urge the designers of computer music systems to remember to consider the degree to which their systems promote compositional virtuosity and the creative power of their users. If the computer takes on most or all of the creative work, that is a valid innovation, but it does not lead human creativity in a particularly meaningful direction. If, however, we consider the role of the human in our creative systems, designing them as formidable machines that resist a composer's initial explorations, but ultimately reward him or her with invigorating and compelling self-expression when they overcome this resistance, we may begin to develop systems that will sustain a remarkable new era of interactive and adaptive musical innovation. Here the thoughtful and imaginative software developer meets the virtuoso composer on common ground, to the benefit and enrichment of music.

6. REFERENCES

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